

« THERMAL EXPANSION MEASUREMENTS OF METAL MATRIX COMPOSITES »

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Metal matrix composites offer numerous options in materials performance over the more conventional resin matrix composites, such as high thermal conductivity. It is necessary to obtain a complete data base on this class of materials. This paper will describe measurements of the coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE). Because theoretical predictions indicate that very small CTE values can be achieved, there is interest in related phenomena, such as thermal cycling behavior. In particular, there must be adequate experimental accuracy to measure these quantities as a function of fiber/metal systems.

The advantages of essentially contactless measurement techniques such as Michelson interferometry are presented, including lack of restriction on sample size or shape. Dimensional changes can be measured with an accuracy on the order of $\pm 10^{-8}$ m. Since differential thermal strains between fiber and matrix have been found to produce stresses which exceed the transverse strength of resin matrices, a new acousto-optical technique is also described to study microcracking in metal matrix composites at low temperatures, concurrently with CTE measurements.

Experimental results are presented for B/Al, Gr/Al, SiC/Al and Gr/Mg composites. The macroscopic thermal expansion properties can be reasonably predicted when the value of E_f after fabrication is reliably known, as for example, when the composite value E_c conforms to the rule of mixtures. The fine structure of a length versus temperature curve requires more detailed analysis, and must consider the possible effects of plastic flow, microcracking, and other thermal fatigue phenomena, such as delaminations.

INTRODUCTION

Metal matrix composites (MMC) offer numerous options in material performance over conventional resin matrix composites, such as high thermal and electrical conductivity and freedom from moisture effects. In many applications where composites are employed as structural materials, the dimensional stability characteristics are of primary concern. Theoretical predictions based on new ultra-high modulus reinforcing fibers suggest that near zero thermal expansion coefficients (CTE) are now achievable with metal matrices. The relative importance of related characteristics such as thermal cycling behaviour, internal stress relief, and thermo-mechanical history is increased. In addition to broadening the data base for MMC, this paper seeks to explore the advances required in theory, measurement techniques and materials understanding.

There have been few studies of the thermal cycling behaviour of metal matrix composites and these that exist have emphasized the boron fiber reinforced aluminum system [1-5]. The matrix yield strength was shown to have a major effect on the CTE. In addition to plastic deformation of the matrix, cracking or failure of the fiber and failure of the fiber-matrix interface are all possible. Indeed, matrix cracking of the type found in graphite-epoxy composites is also found in MMC above room temperature. B/Al systems generally show a stronger metal to fiber bond than Gr/Al, so that mixed modes of failure are found more frequently in the former system. Graphite fiber reinforced metals are characterized by less uniform fiber distribution, and a lower transverse strain capability than B/Al. Inter-ply failure may also be possible, especially with weak matrices such as cast alloys or with cross-ply layups. The ductility of a metal may also be expected to influence the low temperature microcracking behavior.

THEORY

Predictions of the CTE of composites are based on the work of Turner, Levin, Hill, Hashin, Schapery, Halpin, and others [6-11]. Most of the early work applies to elastic behavior of spherical particles in an isotropic composite and requires bounds set on the bulk modulus either through a uniform stress or uniform strain assumption. In case of a transversely isotropic aligned fiber composite with two isotropic phases, a number of relations can be shown to be equivalent, and bounds on the values of the CTE can be obtained from bounds on the moduli. When the Poisson's ratios of the constituents, ν_f and ν_m , are nearly equal, the upper and lower bounds for Levin's original equation [7] reduce to

$$\frac{\overline{E\alpha}}{E} \leq \alpha_0 \leq \frac{\overline{K\alpha}}{K} \quad (1)$$

where α_0 represents the 0° or longitudinal CTE of a unidirectional composite, E the Young's modulus and K the bulk modulus. The bars denote average quantities. Similarly the transverse CTE or α_{90} is bounded as;

$$\bar{\alpha} \leq \alpha_{90} \leq (1 + \nu_f)\alpha_f V_f + (1 + \nu_m)\alpha_m V_m - \alpha_0(\nu_f V_f + \nu_m V_m) \quad (2)$$

where V denotes the volume fraction of the fiber (f) or matrix (m). We have shown [12] that these relations excellently describe thermal expansion behaviour in the B/Al system over small temperature excursions near 300K. For more precise predictions, however, it is necessary to note that while the Poisson's ratios of both B and Gr fibers are generally assumed to be equal to 0.2, there are no direct measurements. Dean and Turner [13] show that ν_{ij} values for graphite fibers can range from 0.01 to 0.53. In any case values of ν_{A1} and ν_{Mg} are about 0.25 - 0.3. An approach to this problem is suggested by a return to Levin's original equation

$$\alpha_0 = \alpha_m + \frac{(\alpha_f - \alpha_m)}{(\nu_f - \nu_m)} \left[(1 + \nu_f)(E_0 - V_m E_m) - (1 + \nu_m) V_f E_f \right] \quad (3)$$

using Hill's expression for E_o :

$$E_o = E_f V_f + E_m V_m + \frac{4V_f V_m (\nu_f - \nu_m)^2}{\frac{V_f}{k_m} + \frac{V_m}{k_f} + \frac{1}{\mu}} \quad (4)$$

where k is the plane-strain bulk modulus and

$$k = K + (1/3)\mu \quad (5)$$

$$K = E/3(1-2\nu) \quad (6)$$

$$\mu = E/2(1+\nu) \quad (7)$$

The subscript for μ in equation (4) will be either the fiber or the matrix, thereby setting upper and lower bounds for E in (4) and hence α_o in (3). Fiber CTE values (α_f) are not known very accurately. There has been an empirical assumption that the negative α_f value is linearly proportional to the elastic modulus (E_f) but in the case of ultra high modulus pitch fibers this may not be true. (Union Carbide reports a value of $-1.26 \times 10^{-6} K^{-1}$ for P75S fibers, a value which may be compared to -1.0 to $-1.1 \times 10^{-6} K^{-1}$ for GY70 fiber of similar modulus.) In addition to the problem of adequate ν_f and α_f values, there is still the assumption in these equations of an isotropic fiber - valid for glass but certainly not for graphite. The effect of anisotropic fibers on the elastic moduli and CTE's of composites has been considered by Hashin [8] and others [9, 10, 13]. Kriz [9], Dean [13] and co-workers show that it may be possible to obtain a complete set of mechanical properties with the help of ultrasonic velocity measurements. With both macro-and microscopic isotropy and anisotropic fibers, Hashin [8] gives

$$\alpha_o = \bar{\alpha}_o + (\alpha_{kl}^f - \alpha_{kl}^m) P_{klrs} (S_{rsll}^* - \bar{S}_{rsll}) \quad (8)$$

$$\alpha_{90} = \bar{\alpha}_{90} + (\alpha_{kl}^f - \alpha_{kl}^m) P_{klrs} (S_{rs22}^* - \bar{S}_{rs22}) \quad (9)$$

where S_{rsij}^* are the elastic compliances and $P_{klrs} (S_{rsij}^f - S_{rsij}^m)$ equals $I_{kl ij}$, a fourth rank symmetric unit tensor. P_{klrs} must be determined by inversion of the transversely isotropic matrix $S_{rsij}^f - S_{rsij}^m$. Hashin shows that in the case of Gr/Al, the assumption of an isotropic fiber leads to the erroneous conclusion that the fiber provides transverse stiffening. In graphite epoxy, in fact, the anisotropic fiber still leads to increase in k , G_0 , G_{90} and E_{90} , but not in the Gr/Al case. (G is the shear modulus.) For oriented short fiber composites, Halpin gives an approximate equation for the thermal strains [11]. Extension of his analysis to consider the case $\nu_f \neq \nu_m$ and an anisotropic discontinuous fiber has not, to the author's knowledge, been made.

The theories discussed are based on linear elastic behaviour of all phases of the composites. Kreider and Patarini [5] point out that changes of $\Delta T > 60K$ are likely to lead to plastic deformation in an Al matrix, which in turn accounts for CTE data lower than that predicted by elastic theory. Models to account for matrix yielding effects on CTE have been proposed by Ferte [1], Kreider [5] and Neubert [14]. In all cases plastic flow is assumed, with changes in the internal stress states. Differential fiber-matrix expansion can also lead to matrix cracking or interface cracking, depending on whether the tensile strength of the matrix or the composite transverse tensile strength is lower. The matrix strength in MMC is higher than in resin matrix composites so that interface cracking may be more prevalent. Stresses may be similar nevertheless, for while α_{metal} is $\sim 1/2 \alpha_{resin}$, the fabrication temperature of MMC are generally higher. Cooper and Sillwood [15] equated the tensile load in the matrix with the compressive load in the fibers to derive expressions for the temperature excursion needed to induce failure. The strain per crack, and hence dimensional change of the composite could, in principle, be estimated by the shear lag theory of Bailey et al [16]. Again, these theories must be extended to cover plastic flow in MMC.

A preliminary approach to the measurement of microcracking onset temperatures, ΔT , and coefficient of cracking expansion has been made in our laboratory [17]. Neubert [14] has applied the same classical lamination theory, modified with a step wise linear analysis involving E_f , E_m , α_f and α_m changes with temperature, to prediction of ΔT for a 45 volume percent unidirectional Gr/Mg composite, assuming a matrix failure strength criterion of 48 MPa (7000 psi). His value of $\Delta T = 610K$ suggests that microcracking is to be expected at lower temperatures than are common for graphite epoxy. In addition, the energy release per crack is likely to be less than in the graphite epoxy case and consequently more sensitive detection may be required.

Additional related factors requiring precise length measurements include edge or end effects, thermomechanical history, and misorientations, especially with very low CTE values. For a unidirectional composite,

$$\alpha_\theta = \alpha_o \cos^2 \theta + \alpha_{90} \sin^2 \theta \quad (10)$$

It can be shown that a deviation of $\theta = 3^\circ$ between fiber and measurement directions can lead to a 6.5% error in the α_o of a 45 v/o Gr/Mg composite. These considerations indicate that a wide variety of theories apply to the thermal cycling behavior of MMC, and verification of these is likely to require highly precise measurement techniques.

EXPERIMENTAL TECHNIQUES

Continuous measurement of the relative positions of two points is required for complete knowledge of the linear thermal expansion characteristics of a material. Reflected low energy laser beams offer independence from shape, size, fabrication, thermal lag and contact stress effects. Furthermore, Michelson interferometry transfers dependence on a reference material to the laser frequency (stabilized in this work on the Lamb dip to one part in 10^9 in 500 hr). When all optics are placed in a vacuum chamber there are negligible errors due to refraction in beam paths, window or operator effects. All (fringe) information is generated at the beam splitters. Figure 1 illustrates the principle of a two channel Michelson interferometer [18]. The laser beam is split 50/50 at beam splitter (B3) into right and left (sample) side interferometers. Designating the sample ends by S, and mirrors by M, it is seen that for the right hand side, the interferometer optical path length difference

$$OPLD_1 = \overline{B_1 S_1} - \overline{B_1 M_6} \quad (11)$$

Similarly
$$OPLD_2 = \overline{B_2 M_5} - \overline{S_2 M_4} - \overline{B_2 M_4} \quad (12)$$

Now
$$\Delta OPLD_2 - \Delta OPLD_1 = \overline{\Delta B_2 M_5} - \overline{\Delta S_2 M_4} - \overline{\Delta B_1 S_1} + \overline{\Delta B_1 M_6} \quad (13)$$

Assume
$$\overline{\Delta B_2 M_4} = \overline{\Delta B_1 M_6} \quad \text{and} \quad \overline{\Delta B_1 M_4} = \overline{\Delta B_2 M_5} \quad (14)$$

Noting that
$$\overline{\Delta B_1 M_4} = \overline{\Delta S_2 M_4} + \Delta L_s + \overline{\Delta S_1 B_1}$$
, where L_s is the sample length

$$\Delta L_s = \Delta OPLD_2 - \Delta OPLD_1 \quad (15)$$

Consequently the sample length change ΔL_s is merely the difference of the changes in the two OPLD's.

Figure 2 illustrates a method to support the test sample. The cross section of the material is arbitrary; the length is limited only by the size of the vacuum chamber (and resultant optics separation) available and by the amount of heat flow the system can tolerate. Thin horizontal Invar or Zerodur support rods have proven highly successful because their low coefficients of thermal expansion produce a minimal effect on the sample position in space, and in addition their supports are close to room temperature at all times. The system employed transfers the compensation path B2-M5 in Figure 1 to a position directly above

Figure 1 Two channel Michelson laser interferometer

Figure 2 A thin test sample inside the two channel Michelson interferometer. Aluminized end faces, polished to $\lambda/2$ are preferable to alternate mounted mirrors.

the M4-sample-B1 path, thus eliminating the effects of transverse temperature gradients in the support plates. Test samples for metal matrix composites were generally polished at the ends to an RMS finish of $\lambda/2 - \lambda/5$ and vapor deposited with a few hundred angstroms of Al. Au or Cr films, useful for ceramic samples, were found to be less successful on high graphite fiber end surfaces.

The accuracy of these measurements, in principle a measure of their traceability to a standard, is sensitive to thermal gradients in the system and sample end face geometry. The former errors are roughly proportional to the sample temperature excursion, so that the total strain values are more accurate at 300K than at 100 or 500K. The sum of all errors for a 250K excursion is about 5×10^{-8} m. An average CTE measurement on 10^{-1} m sample implies an rms error σ_{CTE} of $1.2 \times 10^{-9} \text{K}^{-1}$.

The four photodetector signals can be digitally processed to count automatically in steps of $\lambda/8$ (7.9×10^{-8} m). Figure 3 shows that the analog output of a photodetector for each sample side can be amplified and continuously recorded. The vibration of the system represents a noise level on the order of ± 0.1 V in a 4 volt signal which in turn represents a length resolution on the order of $\lambda/160$ or 4×10^{-9} m. The error in ΔT measurement is 0.7K since it depends on the difference of two temperatures with thermocouples (Cu-constantan) where absolute accuracy is only about ± 0.5 K.

A comparable system to handle larger samples in described in [19]. Here phase modulation techniques are employed for the signal processing. By oscillating the reference mirror, the intensities of the even and odd harmonics received by a single photodetector are 90° out of phase. Again, quadrature signals are needed to measure the directionality of the fringe motion. Length changes as low as 10^{-12} m have been detected in our laboratory. This technique has been used to measure the CTE of individual precursor wires. Figure 4 shows how a 201 Al alloy with 40% T50 fibers (0.68 mm diameter wire of gage length 0.292m was tested. (The CTE from -40 to 80°C averaged $1.72 \pm 0.01 \times 10^{-6} \text{K}^{-1}$.) The lateral constraint on the lower mirror is introduced to inhibit pendulum motions at about 0.9 to 1Hz. Forced harmonic oscillations also occurred in the 5 - 10Hz range, but, whether present or inhibited, they do not preclude CTE signal processing.

Microcracking at low temperatures causes pulses which have a high DC content which decreases as $\exp(-f^2)$. The resultant stress waves cause length changes which are readily detectable since attenuation is lowest at the lowest frequencies. Conventional acoustic emission, besides requiring transducers, operates mainly at frequencies of 150 KHz and above. A recent development [17] involves the simultaneous recording of 0 - 25 KHz frequency signals received by the photodetectors during low temperature CTE measurements. A separate signal proportional to the temperature is converted to a frequency, giving spectrum analysis continuous built-in temperature information. A computing analyzer allows a microcracking or other high spectral content event to trigger a frequency spectrum which can be added, subtracted or divided by another spectrum chosen at will during the experiment. This permits system vibrations, e.g., due to LN_2 flow, to be effectively removed from cracking analysis.

Thin quartz transducers can also be attached for the ultrasonic measurement of sound velocity [20]. The time to transverse a 1.6 mm thick Gr/Mg sample (as in Figure 2) is on the order of 0.45 μs . This time can be measured continuously to an accuracy of $\pm 0.01 \mu\text{s}$. The composite modulus

$$E_c \sim (\rho l^2)/(gt^2) \quad (16)$$

where ρ is the sample density, g the acceleration due to gravity and l the distance traveled. A continuous measurement of E_{g0} on the order of ± 0.98 GPa, or 1 part in 23 is possible. This would enable changes in the (transverse) stiffness to be continuously correlated with temperature, CTE and microcracking behavior. Comparative pulse analysis for each interferometer (Figure 1) could, in principle, provide simultaneous monitoring of E_0 .

Figure 3 Typical photodetector output from double Michelson interferometer. (Two photodetectors per channel are used to determine direction of sample end face movements).

Figure 4 Apparatus for thermal expansion testing of thin wires, plates or fibers.

RESULTS

A. Graphite-Aluminum

Early studies carried out with Thornel T50 fibers gave CTE values at 300K of up to 1-1/2 times that expected from a prediction based on equation 1. (Use of equation 1 is a convenience as it tends to separate out fabrication effects from plastic flow effects during CTE measurements.) These data could be correlated with composite elastic modulus, especially in the transverse direction. Poor fiber matrix bonding is readily apparent in transverse stress-strain testing while fiber degradation due to processing is reflected by longitudinal modulus values below those predictable by a rule of mixtures. Samples with the highest E_0 values had CTE's close to the $\overline{E\alpha}/E$ curve predicted from initial constituent properties (Figure 5). Higher temperature data (to 673K) were obtained for both α_0 and α_{90} for a 28 volume percent T50/201 sample. (A linear variable differential transformer with CERVIT pushrods was used as well as the laser interferometer.) The data are shown in Figure 6. The longitudinal CTE (α_0) agreed well with predictions based on $\overline{E\alpha}/E$ when the change in E_{Al} with temperature was taken into account. T50 fibers approach near zero CTE while the E_{Al} values drop steeply in the region 550-650K. These factors combine to yield a very low α_0 value for this composite in the 450-700K temperature range. The transverse CTE values were found to slightly exceed those of pure aluminum. The α_{90} prediction (equation 2) is dependent on a knowledge of Poisson's ratios. Positive deviations from a rule of mixture CTE can be expected [5,6]. Further investigation of these results with the laser interferometer at high temperatures would be of interest.

The GY70/201 results for the temperature range 295-350K fell close to those predictable by an $\overline{E\alpha}/E$ relationship. In addition, there was no hysteresis in successive heating/cooling cycles. A $\pm 17^\circ$ angle ply layup measured in the 0° direction did show slight hysteresis - the cooling curve consistently fell about 10-15 $\mu\text{m}/\text{m}$ higher than the heating curve at the same temperature for the three cycles measured. Agreement with an Eq. 10 prediction is good if the value of α_{11} is based on the bulk modulus $\overline{K\alpha}/\overline{K}$; that is; $\alpha_{11} = 8.6 \times 10^{-6}\text{K}^{-1}$ (Figure 5) and α_{22} is taken as $25 \times 10^{-6}\text{K}^{-1}$.

The former requirement suggests dependence on Poisson's ratio effects in MMC angle ply composites. The elastic modulus E_0 for these composites followed a rule of mixtures, confirming the value of E_f used in the calculations.

The most recent data were obtained with VS0054 pitch fibers (Union Carbide) in a 6061 alloy. These fibers have shown E_f values in the range of 586 to 760 GPa. Mechanical test data suggest that $E_f \sim 690$ GPa in the sample tested here. The room temperature CTE values fell predictably below the curves in Figure 1 due to the increased value of E_f over GY70. Below 230K, some evidence of microcracking was found in the form of a positive deviation from the high temperature $\Delta L/L$ versus T behavior.

B. Graphite-Magnesium

It can be shown that the transverse CTE (α_{90}) is relatively insensitive to E_f and α_f , so that the α_0 values are of primary interest here. Figure 7 presents some α_0 data at 300K, obtained for a variety of samples employing different fibers. In this case the curves based on equation 1 utilize pitch fiber properties (Table I). As in the Gr/Al case, the lower V_f samples are also the earlier ones, where non-optimum fabrication procedures tended to result in reduced values of E_f . The data for the GY70 and T50 fiber samples would be expected to lie higher than a $\overline{E\alpha}/E$ prediction based on VS0054 pitch fibers. While the room temperature CTE values are generally as expected, the low temperature behavior is more complex. Some $\Delta L/L$ vs T curves for successive cooling/heating cycles appear to be influenced by microstructures. With $V_f = 0.436$ and one ply layer thickness (0.58 mm) there was negligible positive deviation in $\Delta L/L$ during the various cooling cycles; in a three layer material the slope is initially closer to a zero

Figure 5 CTE data at 300K for unidirectional Gr/Al samples compared to predictions based on Eq. 1 and Table I.

Figure 6 Transverse and Longitudinal Expansion Data for a T50/201 unidirectional composite ($V_f = 0.28$).

Figure 7 CTE data at 300K for unidirectional Gr/Mg Samples compared to predictions based on Eq. 1 and Table I (VS0054 Pitch Fibers).

CTE. The latter approaches the high temperature CTE after a number of cycles to low temperatures (about 4 in the case of a $V_f = 0.45$ sample). In addition, this sample (Figure 8) showed discontinuous "bumps" in the curve which progressed to lower temperatures on repeated cycling. This phenomena is not yet explained. These samples had been prior quenched in liquid nitrogen three times before testing. The reason for this was that in the Gr/Al case, but not subsequently found for Gr/Mg, the "knee" in the $\sigma-\epsilon$ curve is thereby shifted to higher stress and strain values. Opto-acoustic emission studies have not detected recognizable microcracking down to 200K. This may be partly because of the plasticity of Mg at low temperatures and partly because the small samples used have longitudinal resonant frequencies ($\sim 83\text{KHz}$) above the sensitivity range for the tape recorder used. Delamination effects, or the effect of a purely Mg inter-layer between the plies must also be considered.

C. Silicon Carbide-Aluminum

Preliminary CTE measurements were carried out on SiC whisker reinforced 6061 aluminum. The whiskers, a commercial product of EXXON, [21] have l/d ratios of 75-100 with 0.2 to 1 micron diameters. X-ray diffraction indicates that they are β - SiC with some stacking faults. Samples with $l_0 = 0.0182\text{ m}$ and 20 wt % randomly oriented whiskers were tested in a quartz dilatometer. Mean α_0 values were $13.5 \times 10^{-6}\text{K}^{-1}$ (293-393K), $15.5 \times 10^{-6}\text{K}^{-1}$ (293-493) and $17.5 \times 10^{-6}\text{K}^{-1}$ (293-593K), with an uncertainty of $\pm 0.2 \times 10^{-6}\text{K}^{-1}$. Use of Halpin's [11] equations with the estimated data of Table I suggests an oriented discontinuous SiC fiber/Al composite would have α_0 values closer to that of pure Al. Further theoretical investigation is required.

Figure 8 CTE data for a unidirectional VS0054/Mg Composite of three ply layers and $V_f = 0.45$.

SUMMARY

Metal matrix composites represent a new class of dimensionally stable composites. Exploration of the theories relevant to thermal cycling behaviour suggest that there is still work to be done to account for simultaneous effects of unequal Poisson's ratios, anisotropic fibers, plastic deformation of the matrix and microcracking. Verification of such theories will require highly precise, continuously recording laser interferometer dilatometers. This paper has described the requirements and use of such devices, shown to be able to measure strain changes of less than 10^{-9} m/m. Some data on B/Al, Gr/Al, Gr/Mg and SiC/Al were presented to illustrate the range of thermal cycling behavior that may be obtained. Future work will include testing of recently fabricated B_4C coated B, SiC coated B and continuous SiC fibers in Ti-6Al-4V matrices-systems for which few data are yet available.

TABLE I

Some Estimated Properties of Unidirectional Composites Related to CTE

<u>Quantity</u>	<u>Units</u>	<u>B/AL</u>	<u>Gr/Al</u>	<u>SiC/Al</u>	<u>Gr/Mg</u>	<u>Gr/Ep</u>
Fiber	-	"BORSIC"	GY70	"SILAG"	VS0054	GY70
Matrix	-	6061	201	6061	AZ91C	934
α_f	$10^{-6}K^{-1}$	4.9	-1.1	4	-1.2	-1.1
α_m	$10^{-6}K^{-1}$	24	24	24	24.8	51
E_f	GPa		515	470	689	530
E_m	GPa	68	68	68	45	3
ν_f	-	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2
ν_m	-	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.291	0.382
E_{11}	GPa	220	200	100	300	300
E_{22}	GPa	145	36	100	34	6.7
G_{12}	GPa	66	48	60	48	4.9
ν_{12}	-	0.24	0.29	0.27	0.28	0.192
F_T^{tu}	MPa	120	50	>100	50	27
α_1^c	$10^{-6}K^{-1}$	8.7	4	13	1	-1.0
α_2^c	$10^{-6}K^{-1}$	15.3	18	24	21	26
V_f	(assumed)	0.5	0.35	0.2	0.45	0.62
1/d	-	∞	∞	75	∞	∞

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